

S-glutathionylation inhibits plasma membrane Ca²⁺ ATPase 4b activity in erythrocytes from healthy subjects and sickle cell patients

Kuntal Dey^{1,2*}, Miriam Pauline Busch¹, Leonid Livshits^{1,3,4}, Ariel Koren^{3,5}, Carina Levin^{3,5}, Max Gassmann¹, Jeroen S Goede⁶, Anna Bogdanova^{1*}

¹ Red Blood Cell Research Group, Institute of Veterinary Physiology, Vetsuisse Faculty, University of Zurich, CH-8057 Zurich, Switzerland

²Laboratoire de Recherche sur les Produits Sanguins, Transfusion Interrégionale CRS, Epalinges, Switzerland

³Pediatric Hematology Unit Emek Medical Center Afula Israel

⁴MIGAL Galilee Research Institute Kiryat Shmona Israel.

⁵ The Bruce and Ruth Rapaport Faculty of Medicine, Technion – Israel Institute of Technology, Haifa, Israel

⁶ Department of Hematology, Kantonsspital Winterthur, CH-8401 Winterthur, Switzerland

* Corresponding authors: annab@access.uzh.ch, kuntaldey.edu@gmail.com

Highlights:

- Plasma membrane Ca²⁺ ATPase (PMCA) 4b activity is inhibited in red blood cells (RBC) upon diamide-induced S-glutathionylation.
- Four different cysteine residues on PMCA4b, Cys-24, Cys-55, Cys-537 and Cys 632 undergo glutathionylation in healthy RBCs upon diamide treatment.
- Probable mechanisms of S-glutathionylation-mediated PMCA inactivation includes stabilization of the auto-inhibited configuration upon Cys537 glutathionylation as well as binding of ATP to the active site due to glutathionylation of Cys 632.
- In addition to the inhibition of PMCA activity, in healthy RBCs, diamide treatment decreases intracellular Ca²⁺ by inhibiting Piezo1 activity.
- Inhibited PMCA activity observed in RBCs from sickle cell patients might result from S-glutathionylation of Cys 537.

Abstract:

Plasma membrane Ca^{2+} ATPase (PMCA) in red blood cells (RBCs) is sensitive to changes in redox state; however, the mechanism of its redox sensitivity is still elusive. In RBCs, two different isoforms of PMCA, e.g. PMCA4b and PMCA1, are present. In the present study, we explored the possibility of PMCA S-glutathionylation upon depletion of intracellular GSH with diamide in healthy RBCs. We report for the first time the presence of S-glutathionylated cysteine residues in PMCA4b. In contrast, we did not find any glutathionylated cysteine residues on PMCA1 upon diamide treatment. S-glutathionylation of PMCA4b was associated with suppression of the maximal hydrolytic activity of the enzyme, along with inhibition of the Ca^{2+} efflux. However, the pump's activity could be restored upon treatment with DTT. The enzyme inhibition was associated with S-glutathionylation of Cys-24, -55, -537, and -632. Upon incubation of RBC ghosts with GSSG, we observed inhibited PMCA activity, that can be partially prevented by prior incubation with calmodulin. This indicates a probable mechanism of S-glutathionylation-driven PMCA inhibition, as well as the importance of Cys-537 as a regulatory cysteine. Additionally, we found that PMCA4b is S-glutathionylated on Cys-537 in sickling RBCs, indicating a possible pathophysiologic role for this post-translational modification. Despite suppressed PMCA4b activity, diamide treatment decreases the intracellular free Ca^{2+} level. This is due either to the inhibition of the Piezo1 channel activity, that may either be caused by the direct effect of diamide on Piezo1 itself, or to the modification of the cytoskeletal protein(s) upon S-glutathionylation, which can interfere with the mechanosensation of Piezo1.

Keywords:

Red blood cells, Ca^{2+} , Plasma membrane Ca^{2+} ATPase, Piezo1, Glutathionylation, Sickle cell disease.

Abbreviations:

PMCA – plasma membrane calcium ATPase

GSH – reduced glutathione

SCD – sickle cell disease

1. Introduction:

Cellular Ca^{2+} signaling requires precise spatial and temporal control over the intracellular free Ca^{2+} ($[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_i$) distribution. While Ca^{2+} entry into the human RBCs is mediated by a variety of Ca^{2+} -permeable channels that respond to various chemical and physical stimuli, extrusion of Ca^{2+} is solely performed by PMCA and thereby maintains $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_i$ in the range of 30-60nM [1]. Among 4 different isoforms and their ~30 splice variants, human RBCs contain PMCA4b, as the major isoform, as well as PMCA1. Hydrolytic and Ca^{2+} transport activity of this pump is regulated by several different effectors, such as calmodulin (CaM), protein kinase(s), acidic phospholipids, as well as by calpain [2], [3]. While little is known about the impact of mutations on PMCA function in RBCs from patients with hereditary anemia, Genome Wide Association Study (GWAS) demonstrated association of polymorphisms in PMCA4 gene with resistance to Plasmodium infection in humans [4]. This fact is consistent with strict requirements for intraerythrocytic Ca^{2+} control during invasion as well as in the later stage of the parasite development within the parasitophorous vacuole in RBCs [1], [4].

Aberration in $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_i$ content was reported in RBCs of patients with several forms of hereditary hemolytic anemia, such as in xerocytosis, Gardos channelopathy, hereditary spherocytosis or non-transfusion-dependent beta-thalassemia, and in sickle cell disease (SCD) [5], [6], [7], [8]. In SCD, inhibition of PMCA activity, along with pathologically high Ca^{2+} uptake mediated by several Ca^{2+} -permeable channels, creates conditions for Ca^{2+} overload [8]. Increase in the intraerythrocytic free Ca^{2+} supports dehydration and sickling of RBCs, promotes free radical production by NADPH oxidase, and activates μ -calpain, shortening RBC lifespan [1]. However, the mechanisms underlying PMCA inactivation in SCD RBCs remain poorly understood. *In vitro* study on purified PMCA showed that this enzyme is a sensitive target of free radical-induced oxidative damage and inactivation, indicating a possible mode of regulation of this P-type ATPase [9], [10], [11], [12]. Zaidi et al reported formation of protein aggregates as well as reduction in PMCA hydrolytic activity upon brief exposure of synaptic plasma membrane to oxidants [12]. Hydrolytic activity of another P-type ATPase, namely $\text{Na}^+ \text{K}^+$ ATPase (NKA), was shown to be redox-sensitive too, and the molecular mechanism of inactivation for this enzyme was recently unraveled [13]. Reversible blockage of several regulatory cysteine residues located next to the ATP binding site at the catalytic $\alpha 1$ subunit by S-glutathionylation [14], [15] has been shown to inhibit the pump's hydrolytic and transport activity. Further S-glutathionylation sites were reported at the β -subunit of the NKA [16]. Redox regulation via S-glutathionylation was also reported for another P-ATPase, SERCA2. Interaction between reduced glutathione and the thiol group at Cys-674 on SERCA2 promoted by peroxynitrite, results in the activation of Ca^{2+} uptake into the sarcoplasmic reticulum [17].

This study was designed to assess the possible role of S-glutathionylation in redox-dependent regulation of PMCA activity in RBCs. We used diamide to promote S-glutathionylation, as this compound catalyzes the production of GSSG from GSH. GSSG, in turn, promotes the reaction of thiol disulfide exchange with accessible cysteine thiol groups, producing S-glutathionylated adducts. We monitored the changes in hydrolytic and transport activity of PMCA in RBCs associated with S-glutathionylation, and the cysteine residues that undergo S-glutathionylation were identified using LC-MS/MS. An increase in GSSG, a condition promoting S-glutathionylation, was reported earlier in RBCs from SCD patients [18]. In the current study, we finally explored the possible pathophysiologic role of this particular post-translational modification by testing PMCA activity and its S-glutathionylation status in RBCs of patients with SCD.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Blood Samples collection:

Lithium-heparin-preserved mixed venous blood samples from healthy donors (with informed consent), were used in this study. Blood of healthy donors was harvested for the calibration of the blood analyzers at the Clinical laboratory of Cantonal Hospital Winterthur, and within the NextGEM study (stud protocol approved by the Cantonal Ethics committee of Canton Zurich, #2023-01135). Samples of five SCD patients were obtained within the Phase IIa/IIb Memantine trial (MeMAGEN - NCT03247218, [19]) that received approval from the local Helsinki committee (EMC-0071-17) and was registered by the Israel Ministry of Health (MoH 001900).

2.2. Buffers and Solutions:

The following buffers were used in the current study unless stated for particular experiment; (i) Plasma-like buffer having composition (mM) 140 NaCl, 4 KCl, 0.75 MgSO₄, 10 glucose, 0.015 ZnCl₂, 0.2 alanine, 0.2 glutamate-Na, 0.2 glycine, 0.1 arginine-HCl, 0.6 glutamine, 20 HEPES-imidazole, and pH 7.4 at RT, supplemented with 0.1% bovine serum albumin when needed, (ii) high K⁺ plasma-like buffer having the similar composition as (i) but having 100mM KCl and 45mM NaCl. Wherever necessary, we prepared buffers containing ethylene glycol bis(β-aminoethyl ether)-N,N'-tetraacetic acid (EGTA) and CaCl₂ at the concentrations required to produce known free Ca²⁺ concentrations. The ration of EGTA and CaCl₂ was calculated using the following program: <https://somapp.ucdmc.ucdavis.edu/pharmacology/bers/maxchelator/CaEGTA-TS.htm>.

2.3. Hydrolytic activity of PMCA

Pseudomaximal hydrolytic activity of PMCA was determined in two different ways.

2.3.A. PMCA activity in hemoglobin-free RBC membranes (ghosts):

The following method was adapted from Lopez et al [20] with modifications. Briefly, PMCA activity assay was carried out as follows: 200-250µg of ghosts were incubated in 1 mL of a assay buffer containing (final concentrations): 3 mM MgCl₂, 80 mM NaCl, 15 mM KCl, 0.1 mM EGTA, and 50 mM Tris-HCl (pH 7.4 at 37°C) in the presence and absence of 20µM free Ca²⁺. CaM, at a concentration of 3 µg/mL, was present in all the assays. The reaction was initiated by adding 2 mM ATP and was allowed to run for 10 minutes; afterward, it was stopped by transferring the mixture to ice and immediately adding 10% ice-cold trichloroacetic acid (TCA). The released P_i was determined by following the protocol from Dey et al [21].

2.3.B. PMCA activity in saponin-permeabilized hemoglobin-containing RBCs:

The following method was adapted from Fenk et al [22], Vincenzi et al [23], and Zemlyanskikh et al [24] with some modifications. RBCs were washed 3 times with the assay buffer mentioned in the section 2.3.A. After that the RBCs were suspended at 10% hematocrit in the assay buffer, additionally having 0.015% saponin, with or without 20 µM free Ca²⁺. RBCs were incubated in this assay mix for 20 minutes on ice to have complete permeabilization. The mixture was transferred subsequently at 37°C for 10 minutes, the reaction was started with the addition of 2 mM ATP and allowed to run for 20 minutes. The reaction was stopped by transferring the mixture to ice and immediately adding 10% ice-cold trichloroacetic acid (TCA). Released P_i was determined as described by Petrushanko et al [14]. The effect of saponin on PMCA activity was determined at saponin concentrations from 0.005% to 0.04% and saponin concentration was adjusted to a level that does not affect the enzyme function.

2.4. Intracellular GSH measurement:

Cellular GSH concentration was determined using Ellmann's reagent as described al [25]. The samples were deproteinized by mixing with 5% trichloroacetic acid. Ellman's reagent was used to determine the levels of GSH in protein-free supernatant obtained after sedimentation of protein pellet as described elsewhere [26], [27]. Non-protein reduced thiol levels detected using Ellman's reagent are mainly presented by GSH in RBCs as free cysteine levels are negligibly low (about 5 µM are reported in human RBCs [28]).

2.5. Measurement of [Ca²⁺]_i and reduced thiol levels by flow cytometry:

[Ca²⁺]_i and the changes in reduced thiol levels were determined through flow cytometry by using Fluo-4 AM and Monobromobimane (mBBr) dyes, respectively, as described by Cromvoirt et al [29]. To investigate the changes in [Ca²⁺]_i over time and the rate of Ca²⁺ efflux via PMCA in the presence of Yoda1 or A23187, the following protocols were used. RBCs were loaded with Fluo-4 AM in plasma-like buffer as above [29] in the presence of 0.1mM EGTA. Afterwards, RBCs were washed 3 times to remove free extracellular Fluo-4 AM, pelleted, resuspended to a 10% hematocrit in the same buffer, and treated with 5 mM diamide for 20 minutes at room temperature (RT). Subsequently, the cells

washed and suspended in plasma-like buffer and the basal Fluo-4AM fluorescence intensity was recorded for 1 minute at medium flow rate using Gallios Flow Cytometer (Beckton Coulter). Then Yoda1 [30] (final concentration 1.5 μ M) and Ca²⁺ (2 mM) were added simultaneously, and the kinetics of changes in fluorescence intensity was recorded for the next 6-8 minutes. The amplitude of the upstroke of Ca²⁺-dependent changes in Fluo-4AM fluorescence was proportional to the activity of the Piezo1 channels, while the slope of the decay in fluorescence intensity reflected the PMCA activity. To avoid possible artifacts associated with the RBC volume changes, the following precautions were taken. An ionophore A23187 was used to trigger Ca²⁺ uptake by RBCs in a high extracellular K⁺ buffer to prevent RBC shrinkage caused by the activation of the Gardos channel. We adopted the protocol from Etzion et al [31] as well as Jong et al [32] and used to measure the rate of Ca²⁺ efflux mediated by PMCA. After washing and suspending in the same buffer, the basal Ca²⁺ level was monitored for 1 minute. Next, we simultaneously added A23187 (100 μ mol per liter of packed RBCs, as this ionophore-to-RBC ratio was shown to be optimal earlier) and Ca²⁺ (final concentration 100 μ M, to completely saturate the pump) and recorded the fluorescence intensity changes for 2 minutes. Subsequently CoCl₂ (final concentration 200 μ M) was added, and immediately we began to measure the changes in Fluo-4 AM fluorescence intensity for the next 5-6 minutes. The flow cytometry data for basal Fluo-4 fluorescence intensity were analysed with Kaluza software, whereas data for the Ca²⁺ kinetics were analysed with Flowjo software (26).

2.6. Intracellular ATP measurement:

Cellular ATP levels were detected in the protein-free supernatant using an ATP bioluminescence kit based on the luciferin–luciferase assay (FLAA-1kt, Sigma-Aldrich). Sample preparation was similar to that for GSH measurements. After deproteinization with 5% TCA, proteins were removed by centrifugation (10,000 g for 15 minutes at 4°C). The supernatant was buffered with Tris-OH (50 μ l) and mixed with ATP assay mix (50 μ l), and the chemiluminescence signal was immediately recorded (Sirius Luminometer V2.2, Berthold Detection Systems). The calibration curve covered from 10⁻¹⁰ to 10⁻⁷ M ATP [33].

2.7. Immunoprecipitation, immunoblotting & mass spectrometry:

Immunoprecipitation was done according to the “Non-denaturing lysis buffer” protocol from Thermo Scientific using Pierce Protein A/G Agarose beads (<https://documents.thermofisher.com/TFS-Assets/LSG/Application-Notes/TR0064-Immunoprecipitation-guide.pdf>), and the PMCA-specific antibody (Anti-PMCA antibody, Santa Cruz; SC-271917) was used for immunoblotting. Afterwards, the same membranes were re-blotted with anti-GSH antibody (Abcam, ab19534).

LC-MS/MS was performed at the Functional Genomics Center Zürich (FGCZ). For the sample preparation, Protein A/G Agarose beads were washed twice with 100 μ l of digest buffer (10 mM Tris and 2mM CaCl₂, pH 8). For enzymatic on-beads digestion, 45 μ l of digest buffer along with 5 μ l Trypsin

(100 ng/μl in 10mM HCl) was added to the washed beads and incubated overnight at 37°C. Next day, supernatants were collected, and remaining peptides were extracted from the beads with 150 μl of 0.1% Trifluoroacetic acid, 50% acetonitrile. Peptide extracts were pooled and lyophilized in a vacuum centrifuge. Subsequently, the dried samples were dissolved in 20 μl 0.1% formic acid. Afterwards, 200 ng samples were injected on a nanoAcquity UPLC coupled to a Q-Exactive mass spectrometer (Thermo Fischer Scientific) for data-dependent acquisition.

The acquired raw MS data were converted to Mascot Generic Format (.mgf) using ProteoWizard (<http://proteowizard.sourceforge.net/>), and the proteins were identified using the Mascot search engine (Matrix Science, version 2.7.0.1). Spectra were searched against the Uniprot human proteome database (taxonomy 9606, version from 2019-07-09), concatenated to its reversed decoyed fasta database. Methionine oxidation and S-glutathionylation of cysteine were set as variable modifications, and enzyme specificity was set to trypsin, allowing up to 2 missed cleavages. A fragment ion mass tolerance of 0.6 Da and a parent ion tolerance of 5 ppm were set. Scaffold (Proteome Software Inc., version 5.3.2) was used to validate MS/MS-based peptide and protein identifications. Peptide identifications were accepted if they achieved a false discovery rate (FDR) of < 0.1% by the Scaffold Local FDR algorithm. Protein identifications were accepted if they achieved an FDR of <1.0 % and contained at least 2 identified peptides.

2.8. Statistical analysis:

Values are shown as means ± S.D. Statistical analysis was performed using SigmaPlot as well as GraphPad Prism10. Repeated Measures One-way Analysis of Variance (RM ANOVA), with Bonferroni post-test if RM ANOVA revealed significance of differences, was applied after the normality of distribution was confirmed. Student's t-test was used following the normality test when appropriate. The differences were considered significant at * $P \leq 0.05$, ** $P \leq 0.01$, *** $P \leq 0.001$.

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3. Results:

3.1. Optimization of diamide treatment protocol to achieve GSH depletion without alteration in intracellular ATP ([ATP]_i) in RBCs of healthy human donors

Diamide is known to alter the intracellular [GSH]/[GSSG] ratio, thereby promoting oxidative stress in cells. We monitored the effect of varying diamide concentrations on intracellular GSH levels. RBCs of healthy donors were treated with 0.1-5 mM diamide at RT for 10, 20, or 30 minutes. Subsequently, the abundance of reduced thiols was measured by flow cytometry, with mBBr fluorescence intensity as the readout. As shown in From Fig. 1A, diamide at concentrations of 1 or 5 mM effectively decreased the level of reduced thiols within 10 minutes. We verified the findings shown in Fig. 1A using Ellman's reagent to detect the non-protein reduced thiols, of which GSH is a predominant species. Exposure of RBCs to 1 or 5 mM diamide efficiently depleted intracellular GSH

(Fig. 1B), whereas 0.1 or 0.5 mM diamide was less effective (data not shown). We also tested whether the effect of diamide on intracellular GSH levels is temperature-dependent. We did not find any difference in GSH levels upon treating the cells with 1 mM or 5 mM diamide, either at RT or at 37 °C (Fig. S1).

Subsequently, we determined whether the above diamide concentrations could cause [ATP]_i depletion. As shown in Fig. 1C, neither 1 nor 5 mM diamide influences intracellular ATP levels.

3.2.. Diamide dose-dependently reduces [Ca²⁺]_i without changing cell morphology as it inhibits both Piezo1-mediated Ca²⁺ uptake, and active extrusion of Ca²⁺ by the PMCA

We examined [Ca²⁺]_i in RBCs from healthy donors treated with different diamide concentrations at RT for 10 minutes using flow cytometry. Exposure of RBCs to diamide caused a dose-dependent decrease in [Ca²⁺]_i (Fig. 2A). Vital fluorescence microscopy confirmed these observations, as exemplified in Fig. 2B. Decrease in [Ca²⁺]_i was not associated with RBC shape changes, as evidenced from the bright field (BF) images of the individual cells and from the forward and side scatter values obtained by flow cytometry (Fig. 2B). In our next experiment, we monitored the changes in [Ca²⁺]_i in control cells or those pretreated with 5 mM diamide upon stimulation with 1.5 μM of the activator of Piezo1 channels Yoda 1 (Fig. 2C). In control cells, Yoda 1 triggered a robust increase the [Ca²⁺]_i, while diamide treatment significantly blunted this response (Fig 2C). In our subsequent experiment, we monitored the impact of diamide on the kinetics of Ca²⁺ uptake and extrusion. The uptake of Ca²⁺ was initiated with the addition of Yoda 1, while the subsequent decay in Ca²⁺ fluorescence reflected Ca²⁺ extrusion by PMCA. As follows from Fig. 2D, the ability of Yoda 1 to induce Ca²⁺ uptake via Piezo 1 channel was compromised in diamide-treated RBCs as was the Ca²⁺ efflux, which was significantly reduced in diamide-treated RBCs. Data presented in Fig. 2C & D suggest that inhibition of Ca²⁺ uptake could exceed that of Ca²⁺ extrusion by the PMCA, and therefore, diamide caused an overall decrease in basal Ca²⁺ levels as shown in Fig. 2A & B. These effects of diamide could be reversed, and both Ca²⁺ influx and efflux could be restored if diamide-treated RBCs were subsequently exposed to DTT to reduce the dithiols (both GSSG and S-glutathionylated protein thiols) back to their reduced state.

Given the fact that diamide treatment significantly reduces both the passive (through Piezo1) and the active PMCA-mediated Ca²⁺ transport in RBCs, we further explored if the response of PMCA to diamide treatment was independent of Piezo1. Suppression of the Piezo 1 channel activity did not allow to reach the same amplitude of [Ca²⁺]_i upstroke in diamide-treated cells as in control upon Yoda 1 administration (Fig. 2D) making the activation of the PMCA less prominent. In our next set of experiments, we use Ca²⁺ ionophore A23187 to induce the same amplitude of [Ca²⁺]_i influx in control and diamide-treated cells (see Fig 2Ei) and used a high-K⁺ extracellular medium to prevent cell shrinkage in response to Ca²⁺ uptake. Under this condition, we confirmed that diamide significantly inhibits the PMCA-mediated rate of Ca²⁺ efflux (Fig. 2Eii). However, we could rescue the activity of the pump in diamide-treated cells by treating them with 1mM DTT (Fig. 2E-ii).

3.3. Diamide reversibly inhibits PMCA hydrolytic activity, promotes S-glutathionylation of cysteine (s) in PMCA4b

Next, we examined the impact of diamide treatment on PMCA hydrolytic activity in saponin-permeabilized RBCs. In the cells pre-treated with 5 mM diamide at RT for 20 minutes, pseudo-maximal hydrolytic activity was reduced to a half of that observed in non-treated control cells (Fig. 3A). Similar to the Ca^{2+} transport activity, we could restore the hydrolytic activity of the pump by applying 1mM DTT (Fig. 3A). In our next set of experiments, we assessed the S-glutathionylation of PMCA in control and diamide-treated cells. The plasma membrane proteins were isolated. S-glutathionylation of PMCA was assessed by immunoblotting in membrane fraction, and after immunoprecipitation of PMCA from solubilized RBCs membranes using isoform-nonspecific antibodies against PMCA. DTT-treated samples were used and negative controls. As seen in Fig. 3B in lane 1 (upper part), we detected the presence of PMCA in the solubilized RBCs membrane fraction, but could not detect basal S-glutathionylation of the ATPase in control samples (Lane 1, lower panel). S-glutathionylation of PMCA was very robust after diamide treatment (Fig. 3B, Lane 2). It could be abolished upon subsequent incubation with DTT (Fig. 3B, Lane 3). In lanes 4 and 5, S-glutathionylated PMCA is shown in two different elutes from the immunoprecipitated samples of PMCA isolated from diamide-treated RBCs .

In our subsequent experiments, we addressed the localization of S-glutathionylated cysteine residues in PMCA4b and 1. To do so, the immunoprecipitated samples from RBCs of healthy donors (\pm diamide), as well as from RBCs of SCD (discussed in the next section), were subjected to LC-MS/MS. In the samples from healthy donors, no basal S-glutathionylated cysteines could be detected either in PMCA4b or PMCA1 (corroborating with our western blot Fig. 3B lane 1). However, we detected 4 different cysteine residues, Cys-24, Cys-55, Cys-537, and Cys-632 in PMCA4b that were glutathionylated upon treatment with diamide (Fig. 3C), while we could not detect any S-glutathionylated cysteines in PMCA1. The details of the unique glutathionylated peptides and LC-MS/MS spectrum are presented in Fig. 3C and the supplementary Figures S3-S6. The reversibility of glutathionylation was confirmed by treatment of diamide-incubated samples with DTT (data not shown). In these DTT-treated samples no S-glutathionylated cysteine residues were detected by LC-MS/MS.

While Cys-24 and -55 reside in the N-terminal part of the PMCA4b, Cys-537 and -632 are located in the large C3 cytosolic loop, which forms the N and P domains of PMCA (Fig. 5). Interestingly, Cys-537 is located within the catalytic domain of the enzyme at the C3 cytosolic loop that is identified as a binding site of the CaM-binding domain of the C-terminus. The interaction between this binding site of the C3 loop and the C-terminus in the absence of CaM gives rise to the enzyme's autoinhibitory state when the intracellular Ca^{2+} levels are low. Considering that S-glutathionylation of Cys-537 could inhibit PMCA activity, we explored a possible mechanism of this inhibition using GSSG to induce S-glutathionylation of reduced cysteines' thiols in permeabilized membrane ghosts. We determined the PMCA hydrolytic activity in RBC ghosts in three different conditions: (i) in ghosts

supplemented with CaM (control), (ii) in ghosts first treated with GSSG to induce S-glutathionylation and afterwards supplemented with CaM, and (iii) in ghosts treated with GSSG and supplemented with CaM simultaneously. These experiments indicated that GSSG treatment significantly inhibited PMCA hydrolytic activity; however, addition of CaM simultaneously with GSSG could protect the pump from this inhibition, indicating the significance of the cysteine residue 537 (Supplementary figure S8).

3.4. Increased $[Ca^{2+}]_i$, inhibited PMCA hydrolytic activity, and glutathionylated PMCA in RBCs from SCD patients

Chronic oxidative stress as well as increased $[Ca^{2+}]_i$ is reported in RBCs of SCD patients [1, 8]. We have analysed the PMCA hydrolytic activity and the intracellular Ca^{2+} levels in RBC of five (HbSS and HbS-beta-Thal) patients participating in the MeMAGEN study [19]. The $[Ca^{2+}]_i$ was determined by flow cytometry, and verified by vital fluorescence microscopy (Fig 4A and B). In agreement with previous reports, we found high $[Ca^{2+}]_i$ in RBCs from SCD patients compared to healthy controls (Fig. 4A). Next, we determined PMCA hydrolytic activity in saponin-permeabilized RBCs as well as in RBC ghosts from healthy and SCD patients using optimized protocol to avoid artifactual activation of PMCA by detergent (see M&M).

Using 0.015% Saponin for RBCs permeabilization, we found lower PMCA hydrolytic activity in permeabilized RBCs of SCD patients compared to healthy individuals (Fig. 4C). Similar results were obtained using hemoglobin-free ghosts prepared from RBCs of the SCD patients and healthy human donors (Fig. 4D). Notably, our investigation of the abundance of either major isoform, PMCA4b (Fig. 4E) or total PMCA (not shown) through Western blotting reveals that suppression of membrane PMCA activity in SCD patients was not associated with a decrease in the respective protein abundance. Similar to the above-mentioned identification of glutathionylated cysteine residues with LC-MS/MS, we explored this possibility in RBCs from SCD patients. Among 4 cysteine residues that we identified in diamide-treated samples, we detected glutathionylated Cys-537 on PMCA4b from one of the SCD patient's RBCs (Fig. S7).

4. Discussion:

The major finding of this study is the demonstration of a regulatory S-glutathionylation mechanism that controls the transport and hydrolytic activity of PMCA4b (Fig. 2D & E, Fig. 3A). The same mechanism is most likely regulating the opening probability of Piezo1 channel, preventing irreversible Ca^{2+} overload upon diamide treatment (Fig. 2A & D). We also suggest that down-regulation of PMCA function in SCD patients may be at least in part due to S-glutathionylation.

It has been shown that oxidative stress inhibits PMCA activity by promoting aggregation of the pump when purified PMCA from RBCs was incubated with different concentrations of H_2O_2 [10].

Previous studies showed that inhibition of PMCA in RBCs upon exposure to superoxide anion, hydrogen peroxide, or hydroxyl radicals involved two different components: the reversible one, which could be restored after treatment with DTT, and the irreversible component that was presumably associated with lipid peroxidation [34]. In this study, we found that diamide inhibited PMCA activity and caused GSH depletion. Repletion of GSH or DTT treatment restored the enzyme function. On the other hand, previous report showed that GSH depletion achieved by chlorodinitrobenzene (CDNB) treatment did not alter the PMCA hydrolytic activity in RBCs [34]. The difference in action between these two GSH-depleting compounds viz. diamide and CDBN, is in the molecular mechanism of GSH elimination. CDBN forms conjugates with GSH that are subsequently not available to participate in the thiol disulfide exchange reaction. On the other hand, diamide catalyses the conversion of GSH to GSSG, which thereafter interacts with reduced thiol groups of cysteines forming S-glutathionylated protein adducts, and in this present study, we confirmed this s-glutathionylation of PMCA upon diamide treatment by immunoblotting and by LC-MS/MS.

It is well documented that, in mature RBCs, cellular PMCA activity is regulated at the post-translational level [1], [2]. Activation of the enzyme may be induced by phosphorylation, by binding of Ca^{2+} -CaM, by Calpain-mediated cleavage, or by acidic phospholipids. Interestingly, regulation of PMCA activity is isoform-specific. While PMCA1 is phosphorylated by PKA, the major erythrocytic isoform PMCA4b does not contain the phosphorylation sequence “KQNSS” and thus is not a target for PKA-mediated phosphorylation [35]. Our study indicates that PMCA1 and PMCA4b, could be differentially regulated by protein S-glutathionylation. While we identified S-glutathionylated PMCA4b using an LC-MS/MS approach, we could not detect S-glutathionylation in PMCA1. This observation is consistent with our finding of significant but incomplete inhibition of Ca^{2+} -dependent ATP cleavage by PMCA in samples treated with diamide (Fig. 3A). As follows from Fig. 2D, some residual PMCA-mediated Ca^{2+} efflux could be detected upon S-glutathionylation induced by diamide as well. As PMCA4b is the major isoform in RBCs, exceeding PMCA1 in abundance, we suggest that S-glutathionylation inhibits PMCA4b, but not PMCA1 activity. Inhibition of the enzyme’s function as well as S-glutathionylation can be reversed upon treatment with DTT. Analysis of the localization of S-glutathionylated residues on PMCA4b may give some clues on possible molecular mechanism of regulation of the enzyme’s activity by S-glutathionylation.

There are 21 cysteine residues in PMCA4b [3], [36], among which 10 are located in the cytoplasmic loop (C3 catalytic domain) between transmembrane domains 4 and 5, which comprises the nucleotide binding (N) and phosphorylation (P) domains involved in ATP binding and cleavage. In the present study, we identified four cysteine residues, Cys-24, Cys-55, Cys-537, and Cys-632 of PMCA4b that are glutathionylated upon diamide treatment (highlighted in Fig. 5A & B). Among these residues, Cys-24 and -55 are in the N-terminal cytosolic part that, together with the small cytosolic loop C2 form the actuator (A) domain of the ATPase. The remaining Cys-537 and -632 are within the large cytosolic loop [3]. Despite the unavailability of PMCA4b crystal structure, it is suggested that Cys-537 is

proximal to the auto-inhibitory locus, which forms complexes with the Ca²⁺-Calmodulin (CaM-BD) binding site (Fig. 5A). In the auto-inhibited state of the enzyme, the C-terminal part of the PMCA docks to the large cytosolic loop [3], [36], [37]. Using FRET, Corradi et al showed that in the auto-inhibited state, C- and N-terminal domains of the enzyme are co-localized [38]. Binding of Ca²⁺-CaM to the CaM-BD site results in activation of the enzyme ([3] and Fig. 5B). The N-terminal part of the autoinhibitory CaM-BD site composed of 28 positively charged amino acids, and interacts with the amino acids from 537 to 544 in the C3 domain of PMCA ([37] and Fig. 5A). The identified Cys-537 residue is a part of this CaM-BD site, and S-glutathionylation introduces negative charge to the cysteine residue, which could enhance the interaction between the C3-domain and the CaM-BD domain of the C-terminus, thus stabilizing the enzyme's autoinhibitory state. A similar suggestion came from the work of Osborn *et al* where they showed that oxidative modification of PMCA reduced the propensity of the autoinhibitory domain to dissociate from binding sites near the catalytic core of the enzyme [39]. However, a high-resolution crystal structure of PMCA4b is required to verify this hypothesis, given the functional studies we presented. Nevertheless, in this current context, a recent report from Hélène Guizouarn group demonstrating the physical interaction of the C-terminal end of PMCA with KCNN4, resulting in the inhibition of this channel activity in RBCs seems relevant [40]. Glutathionylation of PMCA4b at Cys-537, in particular, in RBCs from SCD patients having altered GSH level, could stabilize the interaction between the C-terminal CaM binding domain and C3 domain and thereby eliminate the possibility of the interaction between the C-terminal part of the pump and KCNN4. If this is the case, the following stabilization of the hyperactive state of KCNN4 will promote dehydration and will facilitate aggregation of deoxyHbS. The other cysteine residue, Cys-632, is a few residues away from the ATP-binding Lys- 609 on PMCA4b. Earlier on, we showed that S-glutathionylation of several cysteine residues near the catalytic domain prevents adenine nucleotide binding and therefore inhibits the activity of NKA [14]. Therefore, mechanistically, it is possible that S-glutathionylation of Cys-632 may hinder the interaction of ATP with the enzyme and thus contribute to the suppression of PMCA4b activity. As mentioned previously, the C and N-terminal domains of the PMCA were suggested to reside in close proximity in the auto-inhibited state in the absence of Ca²⁺-CaM or acidic phospholipids [38]. The participation of Glu99 of the N-terminal domain of the enzyme in auto-inhibition was confirmed in a study of Mazzitelli *et al* [41]. This suggests that S-glutathionylation of the Cys-24 and -55 of the N-terminus could also participate in controlling the activity of the pump during diamide treatment (Fig. 5A). In case of NKA, one regulatory cysteine, Cys-244, is localized in the small cytoplasmic loop, but participates in regulation of the enzyme activity along with cysteine residues located in the large cytosolic loop [14]. Further studies are underway to elucidate the role of post-translational modifications at each cysteine residue in PMCA4b function.

While basal S-glutathionylation of the cysteine residues of PMCA4b remained below the detection limit of the LC MS/MS in RBCs of healthy donors, it could be detected in RBCs obtained from SCD patients. Hydrolytic activity of PMCA in samples of SCD patients was reduced compared to

that of the healthy individuals, but no difference in PMCA abundance in the membranes of RBCs was detected between the healthy controls and SCD patients. Similar to our findings, several groups reported an inhibition ([42], [34], [1] and the references therein) while others showed an enhanced hydrolytic activity of the pump, in particular, the work from Luthra et al [43]. One of the probable reasons for this discrepancy could be the type of hemolytic procedures that were used to measure the hydrolytic activity of the Ca^{2+} pump as some groups were using RBC ghosts while the others performed their studies on saponin-permeabilized cells. The concentration of saponin used to prepare the permeabilized cells could alter the PMCA activity. We observed that, when used at higher doses (e.g. 0.4 mg/ml) saponin may cause activation of the PMCA, while the lower doses (0.05-0.15mg/ml) were without an effect on the hydrolytic activity of the pump (supplementary Fig. S2). Apart from these methodological differences, SCD is known for a broad spectrum in severity of disease manifestation. In our pilot study, we detected basal S-glutathionylation of PMCA4b in RBCs from one SCD patient who was presented with low PMCA activity. However, we did not observe any changes in the hydrolytic activity of PMCA in other SCD patients. Treatment of the RBC membranes of these latter patients with DTT, similar to Hebbel et al [34] did not affect the hydrolytic activity of PMCA (data not shown). These findings indicate the phenotypical complexity of this monogenic disease.

Finally, our study revealed crosstalk between the functions of Piezo1 and PMCA in diamide-treated RBCs. Both Ca^{2+} transport pathways were inactivated under conditions of facilitated S-glutathionylation, and this inactivation was reversed upon treatment of RBCs with DTT (Fig. 2D). These findings are in line with the recently published study of Novoselova et al [44]. They observed inhibition of Piezo 1 upon exposing the RBCs to membrane-permeable oxidants (H_2O_2 , chloramine T), while treatment with antioxidants restored the ion channel function. In our study diamide treatment (i) resulted in a trend of decreasing of basal $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_i$ level in the absence of any agonist for Ca^{2+} uptake, and (ii) intraerythrocytic Ca^{2+} level could not be augmented in the presence of Piezo1 activator YODA1 (Fig. 2C). Since Piezo1 is a mechano-sensitive channel, we cannot rule out the possibility that its inactivation, in addition to a direct effect of diamide on Piezo1, may be caused by the alterations in mechanical properties of the cytoskeletal proteins (e.g. spectrin in RBCs or actin in HEK cells) that would preserve the Piezo 1 channel in the inactive state. Although the localization of cysteine “redox switches” on spectrin remains unknown, earlier studies have shown that oxidative thiol modifications of cysteines can affect membrane properties ([45] and the references therein). Interestingly, recent studies indicated that pathological conditions like diabetes or genetic defects of antioxidant enzymes, which create conditions for the oxidative modifications of cytoskeletal proteins, give rise to altered/impaired ion permeability [45].

In summary, we have shown the existence of an isoform-specific regulatory pathway for PMCA4b through S-glutathionylation of several cysteine residues. These residues are localized within the actuator domain as well as in the catalytic domain of PMCA4b. These findings suggest that S-glutathionylation of the Ca^{2+} pump may (i) stabilize the autoinhibited state of the enzyme and/or (ii)

interfere with the binding of ATP to the active site of the pump and thereby inhibit its activity. Importantly, S-glutathionylation may be involved in the inactivation of the PMCA in SCD patients that may be reversed upon de-glutathionylation. Our data furthermore suggest a cross-talk between redox-sensitive regulation of PMCA and Piezo1 activities. Further studies are needed to explore the potential clinical relevance of this regulatory pathway. Those should include site-directed mutagenesis for the regulatory cysteine residues and an in-depth investigation for the redox-induced regulation of Piezo1 function.

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Figure legends:

Figure 1: Effects of diamide on intracellular GSH and on ATP: Intracellular GSH was measured upon exposing the cells with different concentrations of diamide for 3 different time points with two different methods; First, (A) by measuring the fluorescence intensity of mBBr, and depending on this result, by (B) Ellman’s method with 1mM and 5mM diamide as described above; (C) Intracellular ATP was measured upon incubating the cells with either 1mM or with 5mM diamide for 3 different time points as mentioned. n=3; ns= non significant, * P ≤0.05, ** P≤0.01, *** P≤0.001.

Figure 2: Effect of diamide on $[Ca^{2+}]_i$, cell morphology, and on RBCs Ca^{2+} kinetics: (A) $[Ca^{2+}]_i$ was measured by determining Fluo-4 fluorescence intensity (n=4). Changes in $[Ca^{2+}]_i$ were determined using flow cytometry upon exposing the cells to 4 different diamide concentrations. Depending on this result, cells were exposed to 5mM diamide in all experiments below, and $[Ca^{2+}]_i$ was measured with (B-i) fluorescence microscopy (n=3, Scale bar 10 μ m). (B-ii) represents the changes in forward and side scatter data from the flow cytometry when we exposed the cells with 5mM diamide; (C) Changes in $[Ca^{2+}]_i$ upon exposing the cells with Yoda1 in absence or presence of diamide (n=4); (D) Yoda1 induced changes in $[Ca^{2+}]_i$ over time and subsequent determination of the rate of Ca^{2+} efflux in absence and presence of diamide as well as DTT (n=3); (E-i) A23187 induced $[Ca^{2+}]_i$ level and the measurement of rate of Ca^{2+} efflux via PMCA (E-ii) in the RBCs which were previously exposed either with diamide or with diamide and DTT (n=3); Data are presented as mean \pm SD, ns= non significant, * $P \leq 0.05$, ** $P \leq 0.01$, *** $P \leq 0.001$.

Figure 3: Diamide reversibly inhibits PMCA hydrolytic activity and induces PMCA4b glutathionylation: (A) Maximal hydrolytic activity of PMCA was determined in saponin-permeabilized RBCs (n=4) when the cells were exposed either to diamide or diamide as well as DTT; (B) Western blot showing PMCA glutathionylation before and after immunoprecipitation of total PMCA from solubilized RBCs membrane. Lane 1; solubilized membrane from healthy RBCs, Lane 2 & 3; solubilized membrane from healthy RBCs treated either with diamide (which subsequently was used for immunoprecipitation) or diamide and DTT, Lane 4 & 5; first and second elute from the immunoprecipitation of the sample used in lane 3; (C) Table showing the identified cysteine residues of PMCA4b by LC-MS/MS that are glutathionylated upon diamide treatment; Data are presented as mean \pm SD, ** $P \leq 0.01$, *** $P \leq 0.001$.

Figure 4: Increased $[Ca^{2+}]_i$, inhibited PMCA hydrolytic activity in RBCs from SCD patients: (A) $[Ca^{2+}]_i$ was determined with Fluo-4AM in using flow cytometry (n=5); (B) Representative fluorescence microscopy images from one of the SCD patient's RBCs along with RBCs from healthy subject showing basal Ca^{2+} level (Scale bar 10 μ m); Inhibited PMCA maximal hydrolytic activity in SCD patients which was determined either in (C) saponin permeabilized RBCs (n=3) or in (D) RBCs ghosts (n=4); (E) Western blot showing no significant difference in PMCA4b abundance in SCD RBCs from healthy RBCs; Data are presented as mean \pm SD, ** $P \leq 0.01$, **** $P \leq 0.0001$.

Figure 5: Structure of PMCA in closed and in active conformation: Intracellular loop between transmembrane regions 2 and 3, and contains the "actuator domain" (A-domain). The second and largest contiguous cytoplasmic sequence is located between transmembrane segments 4 and 5. This part encompasses with (i) the P-domain containing the Aspartate residue, which gets phosphorylated during activation of the pump; (ii) the N-domain containing the lysine residue that binds ATP. The probable cysteine residues that are glutathionylated upon diamide treatment are highlighted herein. CaM-BD stands for Calmodulin binding site.

Figure 1

A

B

C

Figure 2

Figure 3

A

B

C

Amino acid residue	Ion and m/z	Peptide sequence	Remarks
C ₂₄	831.333 ²⁺	(R)EGDFGCTVMELR(K)	S-glutathionylation
C ₅₅	798.373 ²⁺	(R)DALTQINVHYGGVQ NLCSR(L)	S-glutathionylation
C ₅₃₇	572.273 ²⁺	(K)TECALLGFVTDLK(Q)	S-glutathionylation
C ₆₃₂	805.363 ²⁺	(R)TVIEPMACDGLR(T)	S-glutathionylation

Figure 4

Figure 5

A

B

Supplementary information

Figure 1S

Figure S1: Effect of temperature on diamide-induced changes in RBCs GSH level: RBCs were treated with two different diamide concentrations and exposed to two different temperatures and subsequently the GSH levels were measured with Ellman's method.

Figure S2

Figure S2: Effect of saponin on PMCA activity: RBCs were permeabilized with different concentrations of saponin, and hydrolytic activity of PMCA was determined as described in the text. Data are presented as mean \pm SD, $n=3$, * $P \leq 0.05$, ** $P \leq 0.01$.

1 Figure S3

2

Peptide sequence: (R)EGDFGCTVmELR(K); m/Z: 831.33, Cystein Position 24

3

4 **Figure S3:** MS/MS spectrum showing Cys-24 of PMCA4b from healthy RBCs upon diamide treatment.

5

6

7 Figure S4

Peptide sequence (R)DALTQINVHYGGVQNCSR(L); m/Z: 798.37, Cystein Position 55

8

9 **Figure S4:** MS/MS spectrum showing Cys-55 of PMCA4b from healthy RBCs upon diamide treatment.

10

11

12 Figure S5

Peptide sequence: (K)TECALLGFVTDLK(Q), m/z: 572.27, Cystein Position 537

13

14 **Figure S5:** MS/MS spectrum showing Cys-537 of PMCA4b from healthy RBCs upon diamide treatment.

15

16 Figure S6

Peptide sequence: (R)TVIEPMA CDGLR(T), m/z: 805.36, Cystein Position 632

17

18 **Figure S6:** MS/MS spectrum showing Cys-632 of PMCA4b from healthy RBCs upon diamide treatment.

19

20

21

22 Figure S7

Sample from SCD patient

Peptide sequence: (K)TECALLGFVTDLK(Q), m/z: 572.27, Cystein Position 537

23

24 **Figure S7:** MS/MS spectrum showing Cys-537 of PMCA4b in a sample prepared from SCD RBCs.

25

27

28 **Figure S8: GSSG-mediated inhibition of PMCA hydrolytic activity in ghost:** Maximal hydrolytic activity of PMCA was determined in RBC ghosts in the
29 presence of GSSG under the conditions described in the main text; Data are presented as mean \pm SD, n=3, **for $P \leq 0.01$.

